

The concept of “parallel thinking”, as well as its application and use in the “security” sector’s human resource management

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Abstract

Making good decisions requires the perception, processing, and use of information in parallel, which is a new concept. This method avoids arguing, in contrast to traditional discussions where participants first announce their personal positions and then attempt to defend them. Here, the cartographic technique is employed, in which all viewpoints, alternate hypotheses, criticisms, and emotive opinions are freely communicated by being plotted on a shared map, on the basis of which decisions are taken in order to accomplish the desired outcome.

The foundation of parallel thinking is Edward De Bono’s “Six Thinkers Hats” approach, which may be used for both individual and group work. Group thinking, which allows creative and conflict-free solution-building, lies at the heart of this process.

The model’s application enables all parties to analyze a particular circumstance while taking into account its positive, negative, and emotional aspects, allowing the most appropriate judgments to be taken based on the suggested many alternative solutions.

The use of parallel thinking is common, not just in social relationships and academic areas but also in the administration of human resources in both the public and private sectors. Despite having some features typical of the so-called “power structures”, organizations in the “security” sector still conform to the major principles governing the operations of public sector institutions. The use of parallel thinking in information processing and decision-making by employees of organizations in the security sector will help on one hand to move away from the old debate-argumentative type of thinking, and on the other hand, the very constructions of the sector will respond to the rapidly changing conditions of the 21st century, which are characterized by their liberal views, setting non-violence and protection as a priority.

Key words: security sector, six thinking hats, parallel thinking.

Introduction

The success of each organization, whether public or private, is based on how its people resources are managed. The organizations in the security sector are no different, so appropriate management and employee motivation must take the lead with them as well as with all other organizations. Because of the strong, pronounced hierarchical dependence that characterizes companies in the security sector, management staff is responsible for a significant portion of the management of human resources and staff motivation. Managers must first be trained, possess certain information and abilities connected to personnel management, as well as modify their mindset in order to build a successful and practical strategy for inspiring staff. On the other hand, change and the desire for creative two-way interactions and contacts with customers and businesses presented another of the modern organization’s traditional “enemies” to it in the area of crisis management. New variations in accumulating and providing information are changing the way of life, thinking and work in organizations (Stefanova, D., Vasilev, V. 2022, p. 96).

Material and Methods

The method of the research of the article is also a comparative analysis and differences of interpretation by the court and their application in practice. The main method of the research is a view of some key publications available spots of expertise in management and e-government and smart-goals and other references and their short presentation in the article with two main goals – their distinct indication and their supplementation of each other in the management matters. The materials analysed are in the following key areas: human resource management; organizational behavior; teambuilding; smart goals; motivation and esc. Analytical materials and websites of public institutions have also been used, with proven good practices in the field of public management and chat-bot.

Results and Discussion

According to research and analyses, security sector workers frequently use the strategy of negative criticism based on their emotional-negative feelings while discussing a particular case or looking at particular changes in the way their jobs are organized. This strategy is entirely rational given how much Western civilizations value disagreement and criticism, yet it ignores the constructive, creative, and productive aspects of thinking. Employees frequently express their views in the form: “I don’t know how things should be, but it can’t stay that way”. You must find a solution because you are the boss. It is important to note that while this way of thinking is somewhat logical given that the majority of employees have practical thinking, which is not necessarily a bad thing, it is nevertheless too close to industrial age thinking, as Stephen Covey states on “Walking Job Descriptions” (Kovi, S. 2011, p. 45), or something similar. “Bolts in the machine”, which is too outdated and useless in the “era of information”.

Another issue that has been noticed is that when performing their official duties, a lot of employees frequently make mistakes and don't come up with the best solutions. This is because they apply what is known as “linear thinking”, fail to properly scale the problem, or don’t trust their intuition and past experience, applying the “should be” method, leading to errors from conceit. The fact that the errors here are primarily caused by the way the mind processes information is what matters most. They do not result from a person’s knowledge, carelessness, or incompetence. (De Bono, E. 2007, p. 97). Analysis reveals that poor planning, lack of trust in judgment, and abandonment of responsibility are the main causes of this issue. Unfortunately, not just the average executive staff but also those in expert and professional roles show these mistakes. Because of the significant hierarchical reliance that results from organizing from the security sector, it is essential that employees in management positions first gain the necessary skills and knowledge before applying them vertically downstream to employees at lower levels. The requirement that candidates for management positions hold the necessary level of higher education, regardless of the field and range of knowledge held, must be taken into consideration for this change to be put into practice. Employees applying for management roles should be required to have education in human resource management, it should be mentioned. At this time, it is challenging to implement this change and establish these criteria for the appointment of managers because doing so will face strong opposition from those who have already been appointed and incumbents who lack the necessary education. They have a point in that their career growth and development are constrained in this way. However, these modifications still need to be undertaken if we wish to adapt the sector's organizations to the new trends of the twenty-first century and societal needs. The problem of being unable to advance in a career will eventually be solved because current employees will have the required education. To start, this requirement can be used in the selection of expert and management employees outside the structures of the relevant organization (under the so-called external competitions). Due to the continuous, ever-evolving, and intolerant nature of the human resource management process, currently employed personnel must successfully complete the necessary courses for retraining throughout this time.

The “Security” sector’s structures in general are strong conservative because of their

individuality, and changes with them happen slowly and casually. Nevertheless, the issue of changing one's mindset is becoming more and more important, as well as necessary from the perspective of personnel management. This transformation is necessary because, in the age of information, more and more employees are already asking themselves, regardless of their status and position within the company, "What should be my contribution to the organization?" Taking the place of "What can I gain out of this job?" Creativity and contribution are crucial in the knowledge era (Covey, S. 2011, p. 43). The old and established way of thinking and decision-making based on dialogue and dialectical conflict is no longer as effective because it ignores the creative and the creative thinking, precisely because employees of the new age of knowledge are much more and have new desires for development and improvement. The modern employee already wants to play an active role in the organization's future by developing their career and future in the company. Benchmarking is a form of application that can be used to study other people's experiences. Businesses will be able to use the benchmarking technique in their interactions with other organizations once they have mastered it as a tool for learning from the experience of the better (Vasilev, V. 2021, p. 95).

The "Six" method thinking caps are the heart of the Parallel Thinking concept

Argument, discussion, and disagreement are the foundations of conventional thought. With this strategy, the solution that works when forced into the conversation frequently wins over the best one. In contrast, parallel thinking is a form of constructive thinking at which various viewpoints and strategies coexist to create a "Thinking Picture" in the end.

The "cartographic technique" has a very broad scope, does not engage in debate, and is also sufficiently clear. Nobody around it feels offended, and none of the conversation participants' personal dignity is at danger.

De Bono's Six Thinking Hats technique is a powerful resource for looking for the best decisions from various angles and viewpoints. (<https://www.debono.com/>). It enables different points of view to be expressed in group discussions without the normal or typical employee-dominant mentality. It is a world where thinking is based not only on facts but also on emotions, criticism, optimism, and innovation.

The technique's foundation is consistently thinking in "colors", since each color represents a particular way of thinking. The purpose is to cause us to think in a particular way when we put a hat of a particular color on. When we think about the problem as a group, everyone has the same state of mind and, if we imagine it, is wearing the same color hat. The term "Parallel Thinking" originated from this. By preventing conflicts and creating a symbiotic result, this method of thinking increases team performance.

The specifics of each hat, or any unique way of thinking, will be explained in more detail in order to get a clear understanding of the Six Thinking Hats method and the parallel thinking approach (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edward_de_Bono).

1. White hat

The white hat, a representation of objective thought, is linked to facts, information, questions that reveal particular pieces of information, and, of course, listening.

"Consider a computer that responds to your request for the facts and numbers that belong to it. The computer is unbiased and impartial. No interpretations or viewpoints are offered. The thinking man assumes the role of a computer when he starts wearing the white hat" (De Bono, E. 2010, p. 66).

2. Red hat

The red hat symbolizes emotions and intuition. Even though we are not always absolutely sure of our decisions, there are moments when we feel internally that we are aware of what needs to be done. The red hat is thinking irrationally and intuitively, that is, using a body of past experience but without enough information and facts. The opportunity to express one's opinion is presented when the thinking man starts wearing his red hat and says, "Here what do I feel about this topic" (De Bono, E. 2010, p. 90).

3. Black hat

One of the most frequently "used" hats in thinking and connecting with the logical-negative

is the black hat.

By using Black Hat thinking, we can provide ourselves a logical explanation of events, but we typically use our conclusions to decide why events won't happen, why an idea is bad, etc.

“Most thinkers, both experienced and beginner, feel most at comfortable wearing the black hat. This is true because Western civilization places a great focus on debate and criticism” (<https://www.novavizia.com/metod-shest-misleshti-shapki-na-eduard-de-bono>).

4. Yellow hat

The yellow hat represents logical, optimistic thinking. Carriers of the yellow hat make judgments about potential work prospects and alternatives based on logic. With them, the focus is on thinking positively, constructively, and toward potential positive outcomes.

Here, thinking focuses on potential advantages and the existence of valuable potential.

Then he discovers the foundation for this possibility. It is related to specific recommendations and proposals. Additionally, the yellow hat way of thinking encourages action and completion of tasks. Efficiency is the key objective (<https://hrconsultant.bg/sheste-misleshti-shapki>).

5. Green hat

The green hat symbolizes innovation and original thought. The folks wearing green hats are those who are searching for fresh concepts, looking for fresh chances, using tools to find ways to motivate like brainstorming, and searching for innovative solutions.

The green cap plays the symbolic part of a fresh plant. The young sprout arises from the ground and continues to grow, spreading its leaves and branches in unexpected directions. Rules or Limits have no power over the green hat thinker (<http://kunchev.blog.bg/drugi/2017/10/28/sheste-misleshti-shapki-na-eduard-de-bono-v-pomosht-na-uchi.1574643>).

6. Blue hat

The management hat is the color blue. The blue hat thinker is concerned with how knowledge is organized. When it's time to switch hats, blue hat thinking is what signals that to us. “Think of a control panel. A man with a blue suit and blue cap runs it. We stop thinking about the subject of conversation when we wear the blue hat. Instead, we consider the kind of thinking needed to handle this issue” (De Bono, E. 2010, p. 187).

Applying the “Six Thinking Hats” method has many diverse advantages (<https://exploringyourmind.com/edward-de-bono-six-thinking-hats>).

Conducting meetings that are significantly shorter and more effective is one of them. A methodical approach to issues and solutions. Generating more superior ideas. Increasing group performance. Reducing conflicts.

Applying this method can be challenging due to its apparent complexity and the requirement that it be accepted first by employees in management positions and those working in fields related to professional training. This is necessary in order to create training plans that are suitable for each employee's intellectual capacity. Of course, the role of educational institutions, as well as their methods and policies, are also crucial here (Gigauri, I., Vasilev, V., & Mushkudiani, Z. 2022, p. 8).

The use of “Parallel Thinking” in real-world situations

Even before using the “Parallel thinking” method, it is important to keep in mind the existing challenges in order to achieve the desired outcome. Additionally, many employees are only familiar with and use discussion, an argumentative type of thinking that is characterized by a lot of talking and arguments. Because of their lack of information or refusal to learn, a significant number of employees respond emotionally negatively to any change, rejecting innovations before they have truly understood their advantages. This surely has an impact on everyone's motivation within the firm (Icheva, M., & Vasilev, V. 2021, p. 914). The strategy must be presented by moderators in a relevant, clear, and convincing way, emphasizing its advantages when put into practice, in order to overcome this negative attitude. As a long-time professor and trainer, my experience has shown me that the best results are achieved when using methods that have a more practical focus and presentation of material with the addition of various role-playing games while educating employees from the public sector. When used in this fashion, the Six Thinking Hats Method is appropriate for group activities and

produces excellent results. The ability of contemporary organizations to adapt to the new difficulties posed by smart technologies and the application of the concept of sustainable development is a major factor in the applicability of this strategy (Vasilev, V., & Ognianski, D. 2020, p. 91).

Several areas of the “parallel thinking” method’s use can be identified after using it in numerous real-world trainings:

1. When solving problems

Blue: Outlining and defining the issue. **White:** Exposure to information that is available. **Green:** Highlighting potential fixes. **Yellow:** Verifying whether the options are realistic. **Black:** Evaluate each choice’s weaknesses. **White:** Solution and information comparison. **Blue:** Choose an action to take.

2. An investigation of a problem

Blue: Study area designation. **White:** Verify the details of availability. **Green:** Putting forward hypotheses. **White:** An in-depth examination of the theories. **Blue:** Generalization.

3. An innovative effort to produce new standards, guidelines, and training and career development approaches

Blue: Making the creative work and requirements clear. **White:** Review the relevant information. **Green:** Proposing concepts. **Yellow:** Each idea’s benefits. **Black:** Negative aspects of concepts. **Green:** Take away the drawbacks. **Red:** Attitude toward the concept. **Blue:** Summary.

4. Making choices that affect the structure's evolution

Blue: Determining what needs to be solved. **Green:** Alternatives are suggested and reviewed. **White:** Evaluation of the situation as it is currently understood. **Yellow:** A rating of how suitable the options are. **Black:** An evaluation of how unsuitable the alternatives are. **Red:** Making a decision. **Black:** Analysis of the proposed solution. **Blue:** A summary and a strategy for the following actions.

Conclusions

Searching for the best solutions from various perspectives and angles can be accomplished by using parallel thinking and de Bono’s Six Thinking Hats technique. They give other ways of thinking a chance to participate in group discussions without being overruled by the common or traditional thinking that is present in the group. Fact-based thinking is one of the “Six Thinking Hats”, along with thinking based on emotions, criticism, optimism, and innovation. It avoids conflict because every viewpoint, idea, and criticism are taken into account and a complete “map” of thinking is created. The idea of parallel thinking transforms the external locus of power typical of workers in the “Security” sector into an internal locus, allowing them to become contemporary, competitive members of the “knowledge” age (Kunev, I. 2022, p. 13).

An analysis of the practice sessions conducted reveals that the development of the internal locus of control and the qualitative application of the “Six Thinking Hats” method increases the goal of self-development, increases professional competences, trains employees to think creatively, creates confidence, develops problem-solving abilities, names and manages emotions, respects the point of view of others, and builds appropriate behavior in critical situations. After using the parallel thinking method, it has been seen that employees are more confident in their ability to handle professional obstacles when unpredictable scenarios happen and to balance emotions and skills when making decisions.

Because employees feel certain they are making the greatest and most ethical decisions for the organization as a whole as well as for themselves, the Six Thinking Hats Method offers you the courage to face your fear of taking on responsibility.

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